

Synergies between Exoplanet Characterization and Asteroseismology

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The use of stellar oscillations to study stars

The study of planets outside of our solar system

For more on Exoplanets

1. Books

Part I The Radial Velocity Method

- 1 The Radial Velocity Method for the Detection of Exoplanets
Artie P. Hatzes

Part II The Transit Method

- 2 Extrasolar Planetary Transits
Andrew Collier Cameron

Part III The Microlensing Method

- 3 Microlensing Planets
Andrew Gould

Part IV The Direct Imaging Method

- 4 Direct Imaging of Faint Companions
Riccardo Claudi

Chapters on:

- **Instruments (spectrographs and detectors)**
- Factors influencing radial velocity (RV)
- Simultaneous wavelength calibration
- The cross-correlation method
- The iodine cell method
- **Frequency analysis of time series data**
- Keplerian orbits
- False planets (rotation and activity)
- The Rossiter-McLaughlin effect

For more on Exoplanets

2. Lectures on a basic (undergraduate course)

<https://www.tls-tautenburg.de/TLS/fileadmin/research/artie/lectures/esp22.html>

pdf files and video recordings

Physics of Planetary Systems: I. Detection and Properties

Prof. Dr. Artie Hatzes ([Thüringer Landessternwarte Tautenburg](#))

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Thursdays 10:00 - 12:00

Hybrid Lectures (in-person and via Zoom)

Preliminary Program

14. April	Introduction and Background	Slides (PDF)	Video (mp4)		
21. April	The Radial Velocity Method : Methods and Tools	Slides (PDF)	Video (mp4)		
28. April	The Radial Velocity Method : Results	Slides (PDF)	Video from 2021 (mp4)	Fake Planets (pdf)	Video Fake Planets (mp4)
05 May	The Astrometric Detections of Exoplanets	Slides (PDF)	Video from 2020 (mp4)		
12. May	No class				
19. May	The Transit Method and Ground-based Results	Slides (PDF)	Video (mp4)		

Rough Outline

1. Basics of Asteroseismology
2. What can be done from the ground
3. What was done with Kepler/K2
4. What was done with TESS
5. The future: PLATO!

To know the planet, you must know the star:

The importance of stellar properties

- ✧ Stellar Mass and Radius -> Type of star, Planet parameters
- Chemical composition: The role of metals in formation
- ✧ Age of star: Age of planet and planet evolution
- Activity level of star: star-planet interaction, effects on habitability

Radial Velocity measurements using the Doppler Wobble

Alysa Obertas (@AstroAlysa)

The Radial Velocity¹ method measures the mass of the exoplanet

Observer

The RV amplitude is often referred to as the K-amplitude

¹Because we only measure the component of the velocity along the line-of-sight only the mass $\times \sin i$ is measured where i is the orbital inclination ($i = 90$ degrees you are looking in the orbital plane).

The Radial Velocity Method

Orbital solutions give you the mass function:

$$f(m) = \frac{(m_p \sin i)^3}{(m_p + m_s)^2}$$

$$f(m) = \frac{K_1^3 P(1 - e^2)^{3/2}}{(2\pi G)}$$

m_p = mass of planet, m_s = mass of star, i is the orbital inclination (90 deg is in plane)

To get an accurate planet mass, you need to know the mass of the star!

The Transit method

The drop in intensity is given by the ratio of the cross-section areas:
$$\Delta I = (R_p / R_s)^2$$

R_p = radius of the planet

R_s = radius of the star

An orbital inclination of 90 degrees means you are looking in the orbital plane

Because the planet is transiting you know the orbital inclination. Thus the Doppler method gives you the mass, transits give you the planet radius \rightarrow density!

Accurate planetary radii and masses are important for determining the inner structure of the planet

Hatzes 2014

The limiting factor determining our knowledge of the internal structure of these planets is the stellar parameters

And the age of the planet

The planet ages are important for exoplanet research and these come from the stellar age

- Formation/Migration time scales
- Evolution of orbital parameters
- For direct imaging: Planet masses

The planetary system HR 8799

What are the planet masses?

To derive the mass you have to rely on theoretical models and these depend on the age of the star”

One can use direct or indirect ways to get mass, radius and ages of stars:

Direct Methods:

- Interferometry: Radius. Problem: only works for nearby stars
- Eclipsing binary stars: mass and radius. Problem: not all stars are in eclipsing binary systems

Indirect Methods:

Spectral Type: Radius and mass. Problem: has to be calibrated

Evolutionary tracks. Mass, radius and age. Problem: relies on models

Stellar clusters: Ages. Problem: Stars are faint and not all are in clusters

Asteroseismology is the only means to determine, directly, the mass, radius and age of the star, even for isolated objects

The Basics of Asteroseismology

Oscillations in the Sun
(observations)

Oscillations in a giant star
(simulation)

<http://soi.stanford.edu/results/SolPhys200/Scherrer/index.html>

B. Freytag : <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OxIX3IHUAGM>

In evolved stars the time scales are longer, the sizes of cells larger and the amplitudes larger

Stellar oscillations can be represented mathematically with Spherical Harmonics

ℓ	m_ℓ	$Y_{\ell m_\ell}(\theta, \phi) = \Theta_{\ell m_\ell}(\theta)\Phi_{m_\ell}(\phi)$
0	0	$(1/4\pi)^{1/2}$
1	0	$(3/4\pi)^{1/2} \cos\theta$
1	± 1	$\mp(3/8\pi)^{1/2} \sin\theta e^{\pm i\phi}$
2	0	$(5/16\pi)^{1/2}(3\cos^2\theta - 1)$
2	± 1	$\mp(15/8\pi)^{1/2} \sin\theta \cos\theta e^{\pm i\phi}$
2	± 2	$(15/32\pi)^{1/2} \sin^2\theta e^{\pm 2i\phi}$

$$\Phi_{m_\ell}(\phi) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im_\ell\phi}$$

$$\Theta_{\ell m_\ell}(\theta) = \left[\frac{2\ell + 1}{2} \frac{(\ell - m_\ell)!}{(\ell + m_\ell)!} \right]^{1/2} P_\ell^{m_\ell}(\theta)$$

$P_\ell^{m_\ell}(\theta) = \text{associated Legendre polynomial}$

Specified by degrees ℓ and m and radial order n

Zonal mode

Sectoral mode

Low degree modes

High degree modes

Number of nodes intercepting pole = m .

Number of nodes parallel to equator = $l - m$

Red: high degree modes have shorter wavelengths and do not propagate deeper into the sun.

Decreasing density causes the wave to reflect at the surface

Increasing density causes the wave to refract in the interior.

Blue: low degree modes have longer wavelengths and propagate deeper into the sun.

The Asymptotic Limit for p-mode Oscillations

For high order modes: $n \gg l$

$$\nu_{n,l} \approx \Delta\nu_0 (n + l/2)$$

$\Delta\nu_0 =$ large spacing

Modes are separated by odd and even degree (l). The so-called large separation is between sequential odd/even modes. What we see is one-half the large spacing

n is the radial „quantum number called „order“

The Solar Oscillation Power Spectrum

How do we scale these to other stars?

The Solar Power Spectrum showing the large and small spacings:

Figure 2 Small section of the solar amplitude spectrum (lower panel of Figure 1), showing (n, l) values for each mode. The large and small separations are indicated. These measure the average density and core composition, respectively, and can therefore be used to infer the mass and age of a star.

Scaling Relationships

$$v_{\text{osc}} = \frac{L/L_{\odot}}{M/M_{\odot}} (23.4 \pm 1.4) \text{ cm/sec}$$

$$\left(\frac{\delta L}{L} \right)_{\lambda} = \frac{L/L_{\odot} (4.7 \pm 0.3) \text{ ppm}}{(\lambda / 550 \text{ nm}) (T_{\text{eff}} / 5777 \text{ K})^2 (M/M_{\odot})}$$

$$\Delta v_0 = \frac{(M/M_{\odot})^{1/2}}{(R/R_{\odot})^{3/2}} 134.9 \text{ } \mu\text{Hz}$$

The large frequency spacing is related to the mean density of the star

$$v_{\text{max}} = \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{(R/R_{\odot})^2 \sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}/5777\text{K}}} 3.05 \text{ mHz}$$

Note: The last expressions are two equations for the variables M and R. Measure Δv_0 and v_{max} and you can calculate M and R!

A Diagnostic Tool: Echelle Diagrams

$$\nu_{n,l} = \nu_0 + k\Delta\nu + \nu_1$$

ν_0 = a reference frequency

k = integer

$$\nu_1 = 0 \rightarrow \Delta\nu$$

Echelle diagrams take advantage of the fact that in the asymptotic relationship p-modes are equally-spaced in frequency.

An echelle diagram basically cuts the frequency axis into chunks of $\Delta\nu$ and stacks them on each other

Ground-based (Spectroscopic) Efforts

Exoplanets around Giant stars

Evolutionary Tracks off the Main Sequence

Giant stars are stars that have evolved off the main sequence and up the giant branch

The „sweet spot“ for RV measurements:

Hatzes (2020)

Average rotational velocities
in main sequence stars

Spectral Type	V_{equator} (km/s)
O5	190
B0	200
B5	210
A0	190
A5	160
F0	95
F5	25
G0	12

Fig. 18.6. Computed profiles illustrate the broadening effect of rotation. The profiles are labeled with $v \sin i$ in km/s. The equivalent width is conserved.

Cool stars like K giants have lots of stellar lines:

Exoplanets around Giant stars

b)

Giant stars tend to have an intermediate mass ($\sim 1-2 M_{\text{sun}}$)

But how do you determine the stellar mass?

You have to rely on theoretical evolutionary tracks which are model dependent. More importantly, you need to have accurate temperature and luminosity measurements of the star to put place them in the color-magnitude diagram

Example: The planet around β Geminorum (Pollux)

Hatzes et al. (2006)

The RV variations of β Gem taken with 4 telescopes over a time span of 26 years. The solid line represents an orbital solution with Period = 590 days, $m \sin i \sim 2.3 M_{\text{Jup}}$.

What is the mass of the star? Evolutionary tracks give $\sim 2M_{\text{sun}}$

Stellar Oscillations in β Gem

Nine nights of RV measurements of β Gem. The solid line represents a 17 sine component fit. The false alarm probability of these modes is $< 1\%$ and most have $\text{FAP} < 10^{-5}$. The rms scatter about the final fit is 1.9 m s^{-1}

The Oscillation Spectrum of Pollux

The p-mode oscillation spectrum of β Gem based on the 17 frequencies found via Fourier analysis. The vertical dashed lines represent a grid of evenly-spaced frequencies on an interval of $7.12 \mu\text{Hz}$

The Mass of β Geminorum

Observed frequency spacing : $7.12 \mu\text{Hz}$ $\Delta\nu_0 \approx 135 \frac{M^{1/2}}{R^{3/2}} \mu\text{Hz}$

ν_{max} (rough estimate) = $87.24 \mu\text{Hz}$

From scaling relations:

$$\nu_{\text{max}} = \frac{M/M_{\odot}}{(R/R_{\odot}) \sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}/5777\text{K}}} 3.05 \text{ mHz}$$

$R = 9.3 R_{\text{sun}}$
 $M = 2.2 M_{\text{sun}}$

But we can do better since there is a measured radius for β Gem from interferometry: $R = 8.8 \pm 0.1 R_{\text{sun}}$

Using this with the frequency splitting you get $M = 1.91 \pm 0.09 M_{\text{sun}}$

Evolutionary tracks give $R = 8.3 R_{\text{sun}}$ and $M = 1.96 M_{\text{sun}}$

If you have been paying attention, the observed spacing is $\frac{1}{2}$ the large spacing, but $\Delta\nu_0 = 2 \times 7.12 \mu\text{Hz}$ gives inconsistent results.

$$\nu_{n,l} \approx \Delta\nu_0 (n + l/2)$$

However, this is only the case for non-radial pulsations. For radial pulsations ($l=0$) the observed spacing is the large spacing!

Problem: It is difficult to get an uninterrupted time series using a single site

Solution: Use several telescopes located at different Earth longitudes (multi-site)

Solar Oscillation Network Group (SONG) is a network of small (~1 m) telescopes scattered throughout the world.

SONG Observations of K Giant Stars

Stello et al. 2017)

Stellar Parameters from SONG targets

Star	log g (dex) ^a	T_{eff} (K) ^a	Literature				Derived		Asteroseismology			
			[Fe/H] (dex) ^a	π (mas) ^b	M (M_{\odot}) ^a	M_{old} (M_{\odot}) ^c	L (L_{\odot})	R (R_{\odot})	$\nu_{\text{max, pre}}$ (μHz)	$\nu_{\text{max, obs}}$ (μHz) ^d	log g (dex)	M (M_{\odot})
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
ϵ Tau	2.62(15)	4746(70)	0.17(6)	22.24(25)	2.73(10)	2.70 ^d	75.54(1.80)	11.8(5)	64.8(5.4)	56.9(8.5)	2.67(8)	2.40(36)
β Gem	2.91(13)	4935(49)	0.09(4)	96.54(27)	2.08(9)	1.86 ^d	36.50(1.69)	8.21(37)	101(10)	84.5(12.7)	2.84(8)	1.73(27)
18 Del	3.08(10)	5076(38)	0.0(?)	13.28(31)	2.33(5)	2.30 ^e	33.52(1.77)	7.51(34)	137(12)	112(17)	2.97(9)	1.92(30)
γ Cep	3.10(27)	4764(122)	0.13(6)	70.91(40)	1.26(14)	1.59 ^d	11.17(16)	4.88(22)	177(24)	185(28)	3.17(8)	1.32(20)
HD 5608	3.25(16)	4911(51)	0.12(3)	17.74(40)	1.66(8)	1.55 ^f	12.74(62)	4.89(23)	228(23)	181(27)	3.17(8)	1.32(21)
κ CrB	3.15(14)	4876(46)	0.13(3)	32.79(21)	1.58(8)	1.80 ^g	11.20(17)	4.70(20)	241(21)	213(32)	3.24(8)	1.40(21)
6 Lyn	3.16(5)	4978(18)	-0.13(2)	17.92(47)	1.82(13)	1.82 ^e	13.74(73)	5.01(25)	243(28)	183(27)	3.18(9)	1.37(22)
HD 210702	3.36(8)	5000(44)	0.04(3)	18.20(39)	1.71(6)	1.85 ^d	12.33(52)	4.68(22)	258(23)	223(33)	3.26(9)	1.47(23)

Stello et al. 2017)

Comparison of SONG (multi-site) to TLS (single site) results

Conclusion: Single site observations can produce reliable results.

γ Cephei

Binary

Period	56.8 ± 5 Years
Msini	$\sim 0.4 \pm 0.1 M_{\text{Sun}}$
e	0.42 ± 0.04
a	18.5 AU
K	$1.98 \pm 0,08$ km/s

Planet

Period	2.47 Years
Msini	$1.76 M_{\text{Jupiter}}$
e	0.2
a	2.13 AU
K	26.2 m/s

Hatzes et al. (2003)

γ Cephei

Primary star (A)

Secondary Star (B)

Planet (b)

$$M_A = 1.32 M_{\text{sun}}$$
$$R_A = 4.88 R_{\text{sun}}$$

Space-based (Photometric) Efforts

It is very difficult to do asteroseismology from the ground, the sun and clouds get in the way and these interrupt the time series.

Space-based observations enable one to get nearly continuous observations of stars for a long time. The advent of space-based transit search missions make this possible. To detect transits one requires a long, uninterrupted time series of photometric data. These same data can be used to study stellar oscillations of the transit host star

- Kepler/K2
- TESS
- PLATO

Space-based (Photometric) Efforts

CAVEAT: Both Kepler/K2 and TESS were designed for transit searches and *not* asteroseismology. The magnitude of the target stars and the cadence (frequency) of observations were mostly not ideal for asteroseismology.

However, for a some of the stars asteroseismology was possible

The Kepler/K2 Mission

- Goal: detect Earth-sized planet in the Habitable Zone
- Orbit: Earth Trailing
- 0.95 m aperture Schmidt telescope
- 42 CCD detectors
- 105 square degree field of view
- Stare at one star field of 100,000 stars
- Duration: 9 years Launched: March 6, 2009

Kepler Orbits in an Earth Trailing Orbit

Kepler is a Schmidt Telescope with a corrector plate

Kepler's detectors

Kepler detectors. Note that they are on a curved surface. This is because the focal plane for a Schmidt telescope is a sphere.

The Schmidt Telescope

The Kepler Field and First Light Image

This is Kepler. But what is K2?

Failure of the Reaction Wheels

- 3 Reaction Wheels (gyros) are needed to point the telescope
- Kepler had four (3 + 1 backup)
- Between July 2012 and May 2013 two failed
- Kepler ran in another mode: K2

Kepler's Second Light: How K2 Will Work

Photons of sunlight exert pressure on the spacecraft. If properly positioned, the spacecraft can be balanced against the pressure much as a pencil can be balanced on your finger.

TOP-DOWN VIEWS OF SPACECRAFT

When the spacecraft is balanced, the telescope is stable enough to monitor distant stars in search of transiting planets. A specific portion of the sky is studied for approximately 83 days, until it is necessary to rotate the spacecraft to prevent sunlight from entering the telescope. There are approximately 4.5 viewing periods or campaigns per orbit or year.

CONCEPTUAL ILLUSTRATION OF SPACECRAFT SOLAR DISTURBANCE. THE ACTUAL DISTURBANCE IS DUE TO PHOTON PRESSURE, NOT SOLAR WIND.

Kepler-2 Fields

10,000 stars observed for 80 days

Kepler could do asteroseismology of giant stars really well:

Increasing size
and age

- Amplitudes are large
- Periods are long

Chaplin & Miglio 2013

Difficult: Use ground-based asteroseismic measurements to derive the masses of planets found with radial velocity (RV) surveys.

Easier: Perform an RV survey around giant stars for which asteroseismic data already exists!

KIC 3520661b

Companion Period: 3552 days
Companion mass ($\times m \sin i$) : $18.15 M_{\text{jup}}$

Stellar Mass: 1.48 Solar Masses

Karjalainen et al. 2022

What about main
sequence stars?

The binary system 16 Cyg A B

Effective Temperature: A=5760 K, B=5760 K

Surface gravity ($\log g$): 4.28, 4.35

Log [Fe/H]: A= 0.06 ± 0.05 , B= 0.02 ± 0.04

16 Cyg B has 6 times less Lithium

These stars are identical and are „solar twins“. Why does 16 Cyg B has a giant planet with $1.7 M_{\text{Jup}}$ in a 800 d period and 16 Cyg A does not? Can asteroseismology tell us anything?

Asteroseismology of the 16 Cyg A and 16 Cyg B (planet hosting)

Figure 1. Power spectra of 16 Cyg A (left panels) and 16 Cyg B (right panels). Top panels: 20 μHz boxcar smoothed spectra (gray), with best-fitting background components attributed to granulation (dashed lines), stellar activity and/or larger scales of granulation (dot-dashed lines), and shot noise (dotted lines), with the sum of the background components plotted as solid black lines. Bottom panels: background-subtracted power spectra over the ranges in frequency where high-order p modes are observed.

Echelle Diagrams for 16 Cyg A (left) and 16 Cyg B

Metcalf et al. 2012

Table 2
Stellar Model-fitting Results for 16 Cyg A and B

	16 Cyg A							16 Cyg B						
	R/R_{\odot}	M/M_{\odot}	t (Gyr)	Z_i	Y_i	α	χ^2	R/R_{\odot}	M/M_{\odot}	t (Gyr)	Z_i	Y_i	α	χ^2
AMP	1.236	1.10	6.5	0.022	0.25	2.06	5.47	1.123	1.06	5.8	0.020	0.25	2.05	9.80
σ_{stat}	0.016	0.01	0.2	0.002	0.01	0.03	...	0.020	0.01	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.03	...
ANKI	1.260	1.14	6.4	0.024	0.26	1.94	21.41	1.138	1.08	6.4	0.022	0.26	1.94	23.29
ASTEC1	1.237	1.10	7.5	0.023	0.25	2.00	5.70	1.121	1.05	7.3	0.021	0.25	2.00	7.97
ASTEC2	1.235	1.10	6.8	0.022	0.25	2.00	7.70	1.134	1.09	6.3	0.025	0.25	2.00	8.47
CESAM	1.253	1.14	7.0	0.027	0.24 ^a	0.72 ^b	3.53	1.136	1.09	6.9	0.025	0.24 ^a	0.73 ^b	4.78
Geneva	1.236	1.10	6.7 ^c	0.024 ^c	0.26 ^c	1.80 ^c	10.82	1.122	1.06	6.7 ^c	0.024 ^c	0.26 ^c	1.80 ^c	10.98
YREC	1.244	1.11	6.9	0.026	0.26	2.08	5.68	1.121	1.05	6.9 ^d	0.022	0.26	1.84	3.17
Adopted	1.243	1.11	6.9	0.024	0.25	2.00	...	1.127	1.07	6.7	0.023	0.25	1.92	...
σ_{sys}	0.008	0.02	0.3	0.002	0.01	0.08	...	0.007	0.02	0.4	0.002	0.01	0.09	...

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16 Cyg A

Mass: 1.11 M_{sun}
 Radius: 1.24 R_{sun}
 Helium: 25 %
 Metals: 2.4 %
 Age 6.9 Gyrs

16 Cyg B

Mass: 1.06 M_{sun}
 Radius: 1.12 R_{sun}
 Helium: 25 %
 Metals: 2.3 %
 Age 6.7 Gyrs

Metcalf et al. 2012

From an asteroseismic standpoint there is no difference between 16 Cyg A (no planet) and 16 Cyg B (planet)

Kepler has determined asteroseismic masses, radii and ages for a number of planet hosting stars

KOI	KIC	T_{eff} (K)	[Fe/H] (dex)	Mass (M_{\odot})	Radius (R_{\odot})	Density (g cm^{-3})	log g (dex)	Luminosity (L_{\odot})	Age (Gyr)	Distance (pc)	Notes	Reference
2	10666592	6350 ± 80	0.26 ± 0.08	1.497 ^{+0.042} _{-0.040}	1.986 ^{+0.018} _{-0.015}	0.269 ^{+0.004} _{-0.005}	4.017 ^{+0.007} _{-0.009}	5.754 ^{+0.304} _{-0.322}	2.11 ^{+0.29} _{-0.24}	386.44 ^{+12.11} _{-11.95}	HAT-P7	Pál et al. (2008)
5	8554498	5945 ± 60	0.17 ± 0.05	1.197 ^{+0.021} _{-0.029}	1.794 ^{+0.003} _{-0.015}	0.292 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	4.007 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	3.684 ^{+0.130} _{-0.182}	5.60 ^{+0.45} _{-0.42}	439.34 ^{+13.68} _{-13.68}		
7	11853905	5781 ± 76	0.09 ± 0.10	1.117 ^{+0.021} _{-0.029}	1.555 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.419 ^{+0.004} _{-0.006}	4.102 ^{+0.005} _{-0.004}	2.505 ^{+0.142} _{-0.124}	6.71 ^{+0.77} _{-0.67}	499.10 ^{+15.46} _{-15.46}	Kepler-4	Borucki et al. (2010)
41	6521045	5825 ± 75	0.02 ± 0.10	1.108 ^{+0.021} _{-0.019}	1.513 ^{+0.009} _{-0.012}	0.454 ^{+0.004} _{-0.006}	4.125 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	2.478 ^{+0.112} _{-0.112}	6.50 ^{+0.46} _{-0.56}	310.34 ^{+9.49} _{-9.63}	Kepler-100	Marcy et al. (2014)
42	8866102	6325 ± 75	0.01 ± 0.10	1.228 ^{+0.042} _{-0.040}	1.357 ^{+0.012} _{-0.015}	0.695 ^{+0.010} _{-0.011}	4.262 ^{+0.007} _{-0.008}	2.753 ^{+0.130} _{-0.130}	2.60 ^{+0.56} _{-0.53}	140.83 ^{+4.40} _{-4.50}	Kepler-410 A	Van Eylen et al. (2014)
69	3544595	5669 ± 75	-0.18 ± 0.10	0.899 ^{+0.009} _{-0.009}	0.916 ^{+0.006} _{-0.006}	1.653 ^{+0.016} _{-0.018}	4.468 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	0.780 ^{+0.029} _{-0.025}	6.63 ^{+0.62} _{-0.57}	92.77 ^{+2.85} _{-2.85}	Kepler-93	Ballard et al. (2014)
72	11904151	5647 ± 74	-0.15 ± 0.10	0.918 ^{+0.006} _{-0.019}	1.066 ^{+0.005} _{-0.009}	1.068 ^{+0.003} _{-0.012}	4.344 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	1.063 ^{+0.023} _{-0.034}	10.23 ^{+5.46} _{-5.58}	179.01 ^{+5.46} _{-5.58}	Kepler-10	Batalha et al. (2011) ^a
85	5866724	6169 ± 50	0.09 ± 0.08	1.199 ^{+0.029} _{-0.030}	1.399 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.616 ^{+0.007} _{-0.008}	4.224 ^{+0.005} _{-0.007}	2.577 ^{+0.103} _{-0.095}	3.89 ^{+0.59} _{-0.48}	312.43 ^{+9.75} _{-9.75}	Kepler-65	Chaplin et al. (2013)
108	4914423	5845 ± 88	0.07 ± 0.11	1.099 ^{+0.019} _{-0.030}	1.450 ^{+0.009} _{-0.009}	0.507 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	4.155 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	2.256 ^{+0.115} _{-0.119}	6.67 ^{+0.69} _{-0.62}	473.56 ^{+14.51} _{-14.51}	Kepler-103	Marcy et al. (2014)
122	8349582	5699 ± 74	0.30 ± 0.10	1.068 ^{+0.021} _{-0.019}	1.417 ^{+0.012} _{-0.015}	0.528 ^{+0.006} _{-0.005}	4.163 ^{+0.003} _{-0.004}	1.891 ^{+0.094} _{-0.094}	8.03 ^{+0.80} _{-0.70}	413.66 ^{+12.89} _{-12.68}	Kepler-95	Marcy et al. (2014)
123	5094751	5952 ± 75	-0.08 ± 0.10	1.068 ^{+0.040} _{-0.040}	1.339 ^{+0.015} _{-0.018}	0.628 ^{+0.008} _{-0.007}	4.213 ^{+0.008} _{-0.007}	2.040 ^{+0.128} _{-0.112}	6.35 ^{+1.05} _{-1.05}	464.73 ^{+14.88} _{-15.28}	Kepler-109	Marcy et al. (2014)
244	4349452	6270 ± 79	-0.04 ± 0.10	1.159 ^{+0.040} _{-0.051}	1.297 ^{+0.015} _{-0.015}	0.745 ^{+0.009} _{-0.010}	4.275 ^{+0.007} _{-0.008}	2.406 ^{+0.126} _{-0.128}	3.45 ^{+0.81} _{-0.72}	247.49 ^{+7.96} _{-7.96}	Kepler-25	Steffen et al. (2012)
245	8478994	5417 ± 75	-0.32 ± 0.07	0.810 ^{+0.003} _{-0.011}	0.772 ^{+0.003} _{-0.006}	2.486 ^{+0.022} _{-0.025}	4.570 ^{+0.003} _{-0.025}	1.967 ^{+0.023} _{-0.025}	5.35 ^{+0.91} _{-1.01}	63.96 ^{+1.93} _{-1.98}	Kepler-37	Barclay et al. (2013)
246	11295426	5793 ± 74	0.12 ± 0.07	1.068 ^{+0.011} _{-0.019}	1.237 ^{+0.006} _{-0.006}	0.795 ^{+0.005} _{-0.011}	4.280 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	1.581 ^{+0.043} _{-0.040}	6.31 ^{+0.32} _{-0.34}	139.77 ^{+4.25} _{-4.25}	Kepler-68	Gilliland et al. (2013)
260	8292840	6239 ± 94	-0.14 ± 0.10	1.148 ^{+0.051} _{-0.049}	1.345 ^{+0.015} _{-0.018}	0.666 ^{+0.010} _{-0.010}	4.240 ^{+0.008} _{-0.008}	2.636 ^{+0.148} _{-0.142}	3.85 ^{+0.81} _{-0.75}	240.28 ^{+7.69} _{-7.89}	Kepler-126	Rowe et al. (2014)
262	11807274	6225 ± 75	-0.00 ± 0.08	1.239 ^{+0.049} _{-0.040}	1.582 ^{+0.015} _{-0.021}	0.444 ^{+0.007} _{-0.007}	4.135 ^{+0.007} _{-0.009}	3.466 ^{+0.167} _{-0.157}	3.59 ^{+0.78} _{-0.45}	251.15 ^{+7.90} _{-8.24}	Kepler-50	Steffen et al. (2013)
263	10514430	5784 ± 98	-0.11 ± 0.11	1.059 ^{+0.040} _{-0.021}	1.590 ^{+0.015} _{-0.018}	0.374 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	4.061 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	2.634 ^{+0.151} _{-0.124}	7.84 ^{+0.40} _{-0.91}	211.53 ^{+6.65} _{-6.78}	False-positive ^b	
268	3425851	6343 ± 85	-0.04 ± 0.10	1.178 ^{+0.049} _{-0.049}	1.360 ^{+0.018} _{-0.018}	0.668 ^{+0.009} _{-0.008}	4.243 ^{+0.008} _{-0.008}	2.728 ^{+0.162} _{-0.157}	3.32 ^{+0.85} _{-0.64}	244.81 ^{+7.82} _{-8.03}		
269	7670943	6463 ± 110	0.09 ± 0.11	1.239 ^{+0.040} _{-0.051}	1.417 ^{+0.015} _{-0.015}	0.616 ^{+0.009} _{-0.021}	4.228 ^{+0.008} _{-0.017}	3.039 ^{+0.167} _{-0.173}	2.78 ^{+0.62} _{-0.51}	331.99 ^{+10.56} _{-11.11}		
274	8077137	6072 ± 75	-0.09 ± 0.10	1.117 ^{+0.040} _{-0.049}	1.632 ^{+0.018} _{-0.019}	0.361 ^{+0.006} _{-0.010}	4.056 ^{+0.013} _{-0.010}	3.183 ^{+0.293} _{-0.202}	6.23 ^{+0.56} _{-1.23}	413.44 ^{+13.21} _{-12.61}	Kepler-128	Xie (2014)
275	10586004	5770 ± 83	0.29 ± 0.10	1.178 ^{+0.021} _{-0.030}	1.653 ^{+0.009} _{-0.012}	0.367 ^{+0.004} _{-0.005}	4.071 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	2.749 ^{+0.151} _{-0.155}	6.43 ^{+0.64} _{-0.61}	402.73 ^{+12.28} _{-12.43}	Kepler-129	Rowe et al. (2014)
276	11133306	5982 ± 82	-0.02 ± 0.10	1.059 ^{+0.040} _{-0.030}	1.189 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.891 ^{+0.008} _{-0.009}	4.314 ^{+0.004} _{-0.007}	1.628 ^{+0.092} _{-0.079}	5.14 ^{+0.86} _{-0.88}	331.57 ^{+10.50} _{-10.50}		
277	11401755	5911 ± 66	-0.20 ± 0.06	1.059 ^{+0.030} _{-0.021}	1.632 ^{+0.015} _{-0.021}	0.346 ^{+0.003} _{-0.006}	4.039 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	2.982 ^{+0.144} _{-0.148}	7.10 ^{+0.61} _{-0.59}	514.89 ^{+16.15} _{-16.81}	Kepler-36	Carter et al. (2012)
280	4141376	6134 ± 91	-0.24 ± 0.10	1.019 ^{+0.021} _{-0.030}	1.039 ^{+0.009} _{-0.009}	1.278 ^{+0.011} _{-0.013}	4.412 ^{+0.003} _{-0.004}	1.363 ^{+0.052} _{-0.056}	3.27 ^{+0.59} _{-0.64}	222.15 ^{+6.94} _{-6.94}		
281	4143755	5622 ± 106	-0.40 ± 0.11	0.918 ^{+0.021} _{-0.030}	1.414 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.456 ^{+0.006} _{-0.006}	4.102 ^{+0.001} _{-0.002}	1.997 ^{+0.029} _{-0.038}	11.27 ^{+1.50} _{-1.35}	360.19 ^{+11.23} _{-11.30}		
285	6196457	5871 ± 94	0.17 ± 0.11	1.209 ^{+0.019} _{-0.030}	1.716 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.335 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	4.049 ^{+0.004} _{-0.005}	3.316 ^{+0.185} _{-0.164}	5.52 ^{+0.51} _{-0.48}	448.57 ^{+13.82} _{-13.82}	Kepler-92	Xie (2014)
288	9592705	6174 ± 92	0.22 ± 0.10	1.509 ^{+0.029} _{-0.021}	2.124 ^{+0.003} _{-0.015}	0.221 ^{+0.003} _{-0.003}	3.961 ^{+0.004} _{-0.003}	6.088 ^{+0.227} _{-0.247}	2.33 ^{+0.18} _{-0.16}	428.89 ^{+13.22} _{-13.09}		
370	8494142	6144 ± 106	0.13 ± 0.10	1.418 ^{+0.030} _{-0.019}	1.887 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.298 ^{+0.005} _{-0.004}	4.038 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	4.818 ^{+0.259} _{-0.243}	2.62 ^{+0.26} _{-0.24}	584.10 ^{+17.91} _{-17.91}	Kepler-145	Xie (2014)
974	9414417	6253 ± 75	-0.13 ± 0.10	1.387 ^{+0.021} _{-0.009}	1.914 ^{+0.015} _{-0.015}	0.280 ^{+0.004} _{-0.005}	4.017 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	5.343 ^{+0.157} _{-0.157}	2.65 ^{+0.14} _{-0.16}	232.81 ^{+7.22} _{-7.22}		
975	3632418	6305 ± 50	-0.03 ± 0.10	1.408 ^{+0.021} _{-0.030}	1.902 ^{+0.012} _{-0.012}	0.287 ^{+0.004} _{-0.010}	4.026 ^{+0.004} _{-0.004}	5.188 ^{+0.142} _{-0.128}	2.60 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	114.49 ^{+3.60} _{-3.51}	Kepler-21	Howell et al. (2012)
1612	10963065	6104 ± 74	-0.20 ± 0.10	1.089 ^{+0.019} _{-0.030}	1.228 ^{+0.012} _{-0.009}	0.823 ^{+0.010} _{-0.009}	4.293 ^{+0.004} _{-0.003}	1.961 ^{+0.058} _{-0.058}	4.18 ^{+0.53} _{-0.35}	92.37 ^{+2.91} _{-2.85}	Kepler-408	Marcy et al. (2014)
1925	9955598	5460 ± 75	0.08 ± 0.10	0.890 ^{+0.009} _{-0.011}	0.883 ^{+0.003} _{-0.006}	1.821 ^{+0.018} _{-0.018}	4.495 ^{+0.002} _{-0.002}	0.598 ^{+0.025} _{-0.023}	6.98 ^{+0.40} _{-0.50}	66.80 ^{+2.02} _{-2.05}	Kepler-409	Marcy et al. (2014)
3158	6278762	5046 ± 74	-0.37 ± 0.09	0.739 ^{+0.009} _{-0.011}	0.748 ^{+0.006} _{-0.003}	2.498 ^{+0.018} _{-0.025}	4.560 ^{+0.003} _{-0.002}	0.341 ^{+0.020} _{-0.020}	11.54 ^{+0.99} _{-0.94}	32.90 ^{+1.02} _{-1.00}	Kepler-444	Campante et al. (2015)

Interestingly, these show a bimodal distribution of ages

The Value of Precise Planet Radii: Internal structure

Currently the uncertainty in M and R (mostly M) are dominated by the measurement errors. Even if these are zero, the uncertainty in the stellar R and M become important

The Value of Precise Planet Radii: The Radius Valley

Photo-evaporation models of planets predicted that some close in planets would lose their entire atmosphere (Lopez & Fortney 2013, Owens and Wu 2013, Jin et al. 2014)

Thick atmosphere:
Stable Neptune

Thin atmosphere:
Unstable

Stripped core planet:
Rocky

Photoionization converts one
type of planet into the other

A small atmosphere has a large effect on the radius:

Fulton et al. (2017)

A rocky planet ($M = 2 M_{\text{earth}}$) with no atmosphere has a radius of $1.2 R_{\text{earth}}$
A rocky planet with an envelope (atmosphere) of 4% (total mass = $2.08 M_{\text{earth}}$)
has a radius of $3 R_{\text{earth}}$!

The Radius Valley: Theoretical predictions

Photo-evaporation results in a lack of planets around $2 R_{\text{earth}}$, a so-called “radius valley”

The Radius Valley: Observational evidence

Early Kepler results were disappointing:

From Van Eylen: Planet-Star Connections in the Era of TESS and Gaia, KITP, 2019
<https://www.kitp.ucsb.edu/activities/exostar-c19>

With spectroscopy and Gaia things are looking better:

From Van Eylen: Planet-Star Connections in the Era of TESS and Gaia, KITP, 2019
<https://www.kitp.ucsb.edu/activities/exostar-c19>

With asteroseismology things the gap comes clearly in view:

From Van Eylen: Planet-Star Connections in the Era of TESS and Gaia, KITP, 2019
<https://www.kitp.ucsb.edu/activities/exostar-c19>

The “asteroseismic” radius valley

Van Eylen et al. 2018b

To make progress in understanding planet formation we need asteroseismology!

Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (NASA)

- All sky survey: 26 fields of 100,000 stars
- 27 Days of continuous observations
- 2:1 resonance with moon's orbit
- Stars brighter than $V = 11$

The Orbit of TESS

- Orbital Period = 13.7 d
- Sky tiled into 26 segments
- 27 d observing period per segment
- At ecliptic poles segments overlap and you can get coverage of 100 d or more

The First Light Images of TESS

The Potential of TESS for Asteroseismology: The value of long time series observations¹

Observations every 2 min

T = 27 d

T = 351 d

$${}^1\sigma_{\text{sys}} = 60 \text{ ppm hr}^{1/2}$$

Campante et al. 2016

The Potential of TESS for Asteroseismology: The value of high cadence observations

351 d of observations

$\Delta T = 2$ min

$\Delta T = 30$ min

An efficient asteroseismic mission should have high cadence and a long time series!

Asteroseismic yield of known exoplanets

Campante et al. 2016

The transiting planet π Men c

Hatzes et al. (2022)

Gandolfi et al. (2018)

Planet mass = $3.63 \pm 0.038 M_{\text{earth}}$

Planet radius = $2.145 \pm 0.0015 R_{\text{earth}}$

TESS Asteroseismic results for π Men

Huang et al. (2018)

$$M_{\text{star}} = 1.091 \pm 0.026 M_{\text{sun}}$$
$$R_{\text{star}} = 1.136 \pm 0.009 R_{\text{sun}}$$
$$\text{Age} = 3.8 \pm 0.07 \text{ Gyrs}$$

Asteroseismology and the Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect

As the companion crosses the star the observed radial velocity goes from + to - (as the planet moves towards you the star is moving away). The companion covers part of the star that is rotating towards you. You see more positive velocities from the receding portion of the star) you thus see a displacement to + RV.

When the companion covers the receding portion of the star, you see more negative velocities of the star rotating towards you. You thus see a displacement to negative RV.

The effect was discovered in 1924 independently by Rossiter and McClaughlin

ON THE DETECTION OF AN EFFECT OF ROTATION DURING ECLIPSE IN THE VELOCITY OF THE BRIGHTER COMPONENT OF BETA LYRAE, AND ON THE CONSTANCY OF VELOCITY OF THIS SYSTEM

By R. A. ROSSITER

ABSTRACT

The spectroscopic velocity of the Beta Lyrae system.—Elements from a series of spectrograms taken at the Allegheny Observatory in 1907 and from seven series, comprising a total of 442 spectrograms, taken at Ann Arbor in the years 1911 to 1921, show that the velocity of the center of mass of the system is constant and that elliptical motion is very well satisfied. Probably no third body exists, since no disturbance of the two-body system can be detected. The accompanying elliptic velocity curve, with radial velocities indicated by the large dots, shows how well elliptical motion is satisfied.

The rotational effect.—A secondary oscillation confined to the region of the velocity curve extending 1.6 days on each side of the principal minimum (or center of the eclipse of the small bright body by the large faint body) has been isolated from the orbital velocity and measured. It has been shown to be due to the velocity of rotation of the partially eclipsed smaller component, and is here termed the rotational effect. In Beta Lyrae it has a total range of 26 kilometers. A graphical determination of this curve of rotational velocity from Shapley's light-elements of Beta Lyrae gives a duration of eclipse 40 per cent longer than the spectroscope has shown and an amplitude correspondingly too great. Further investigation of this subject is under way.

FIG. 2

Curves show Radial Velocity after removing the binary orbital motion

SOME RESULTS OF A SPECTROGRAPHIC STUDY OF THE ALGOL SYSTEM

By DEAN B. McLAUGHLIN

ABSTRACT

One hundred and fifty-six plates taken in 1913, 1920, and 1923 with the one-prism spectrograph of the Detroit Observatory form the basis of this discussion.

Short- and long-period orbits.—From plates taken within one month in 1923 orbital elements of the eclipsing system are determined. The value of $a \sin i$ is larger than in previous determinations. With these elements as standard the velocity of the center of mass is derived for other epochs by means of simple residuals. A period of about 1.885 years and a range of 20 km are indicated for the variation of the velocity of the center of mass of the eclipsing system, substantially in agreement with the determination by R. H. Curtiss.

Rotational effect.—This effect due to the rotation of the brighter star during the partial eclipse, discovered by Dr. Rossiter in Beta Lyrae, is investigated in Algol and is found to have a range of 35 km as shown in the diagram. Computation with Stebbins' light-elements gives only half the observed range of the effect, on assumption that $m_b = 2m_f$. Investigation of this rotational effect is suggested as a means of determining dimensions of other eclipsing systems. Agreement of form of computed and observed curves serves as a check on light-elements.

Dimensions of the eclipsing system.—Assuming equal periods of revolution and rotation of the bright star the dimensions of the eclipsing system are calculated. The total mass is $5.67 \odot$. Mass ratio is $m_b = 5.0 m_f$. Radii of the stars are: $r_b = 3.12 \odot$, and $r_f = 3.68 \odot$. Distance between centers: 10,522,000 km. Densities: $d_b = 0.16$, $d_f = 0.02$ ($\odot = 1$).

Parallax.—Hypothetical parallax of Algol is $0''.031$. Orbital motion is suggested as a possible cause of negative parallaxes of certain stars.

FIG. 1.—Curve of the rotational effect in Algol

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect in an Eclipsing Binary

From Holger Lehmann

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect is a „Rotation Effect“ due to stellar rotation

Amplitude of the R-M effect:

$$A_{RV} = 52.8 \text{ m s}^{-1} \left(\frac{V_s}{5 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right) \left(\frac{r}{R_{\text{Jup}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{R}{R_{\odot}} \right)^{-2}$$

A_{RV} is amplitude after removal of orbital motion

V_s is rotational velocity of star in km s^{-1}

r is radius of planet divided by Jupiter radius R_{Jup}

R is the stellar radius divided by solar radius R_{\odot}

Note:

1. The Amplitude of the R-M effect depends on the radius of the planet and not its mass.
2. As with photometric transits the amplitude is proportional to the ratio of the disk area of the planet and star.
3. The R-M effect is proportional to the rotational velocity of the star. If the star has little rotation, it will not show a R-M effect.

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect

What can the RM effect tell you?

1) The orbital inclination or impact parameter

Figures inspired from Josh Winn

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect

2) The direction of the orbit

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect

2) The alignment of the orbit

The Rossiter-McLaughlin Effect in HD 209458

The photometric transit

The Radial Velocity Orbit

The spectroscopic transit

Amplitude is ≈ 50 m/s, $v \sin i = 4.5$ km/s, Radius of star = 1.15 Solar radii \Rightarrow radius of planet $\approx 1.4 R_{\text{Jup}}$

$$\lambda = -0.1 \pm 2.4 \text{ deg}$$

Queloz et al. (2000)

A misaligned planet in CoRoT-1b

Lambda ~ 80 deg!

HAT-P7: The backwards planet

$\lambda = 182 \text{ deg!}$

Orbit oriented system

We want to measure the true angle between the orbital axis of the planet and the spin axis of the star, ψ

Observer oriented system

But because we measure the projected rotational velocity of the star, we do not know the true stellar inclination. We measure λ , but we want star, ψ

To get this we need to know the true inclination of the star!

The true is related to λ , stellar inclination, i_* , orbit inclination i by:

$$\cos \psi = \cos i_* \cos i + \sin i_* \sin i \cos \lambda$$

Star

Transit fit

R-M

Fabrycky & Winn (2009)

If you know the true rotational velocity of the star, you can calculate the rotation angles of the star:

E.g. HAT-P7 has a projected rotational velocity of 4 km/s which is low for its spectral type of F6V. Average for an F6V stars is about 10-20 km/s

If real rotational velocity of star = 20 km/s, and the projected rotational velocity is 4 km/s, then the inclination axis of the star is $\arcsin(4/20) \rightarrow i_s = 11$ degrees \rightarrow we are viewing HAT-P7 nearly pole-on from the rotation axis

So is HAT-P7 really in a retrograde orbit?

Using asteroseismology to get the inclination of the star

No rotation

rotation

$l = 0$
 $m = 0$

$\Delta\nu$

Modes have
values from
 $-l$ to $+l$

$l = 1$
 $m = -1, 0, +1$

Rotation splits the degeneracy of the “ m ” levels, analogous to Zeeman splitting of energy levels of an atom

$\Delta\nu$ is proportional to the rotational velocity of the star

The stellar inclination affects the amplitudes of the sidelobes:

ESA's PLATO Mission:

The recognition of the importance of asteroseismology for exoplanet science

Why so many telescopes (26) 12 cm diameter telescopes?

26 12-cm telescopes have the same collecting area as one 60 cm telescope.
Why not just build a single 60cm telescope?

PLATO will observe stars brighter than $V = 11$ mag. Bright stars are spread out over a wide field across the sky

Field of View (FoV) 12-cm telescope:
~6 deg (diameter) assuming a single detector

Field of View (FoV) 60-cm telescope:
~1.2 deg

But a small telescope collects fewer photons.

Solution: Use many small telescopes!

The PLATO Mission

Launch in 2026

PLATO :

- planets around bright stars
- astroseismology of hosts
- ultra-high precision
- very wide field

Accuracy:

An Earth around a Sun :

- radius up to 2%
- mass up to 10%
- age known to 10%

The Plato Fields

PLATO will produce this, but for main sequence stars

Kallinger et al. 2010

“I think this is the beginning of a beautiful friendship.”

Astroseismology

Exoplanets